

TRANSFORMATION IN TRANSLATING LITERARY TEXTS FROM ENGLISH INTO UZBEK

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Abstract. *The article discusses translation changes in literary texts, which are unavoidable when information is transferred from English into Uzbek, giving linguists a huge amount of empirical data for their study. Translators are inevitably forced to use a variety of "transformations" to achieve pragmatic adaptation of the text. A skilled translator should accurately translate the original text with clarity, while preserving the highest level of adequacy. Overcoming the subjectivism and random mistakes of the author is a necessity when utilizing translation as a source for linguistic study.*

Key words: *source text, transformations, methods, lexical transformation, substitutions, addition, omission, equivalence, semantic components.*

ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ В ПЕРЕВОДЕ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННЫХ ТЕКСТОВ С АНГЛИЙСКОГО НА УЗБЕКСКИЙ ЯЗЫК

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются переводческие изменения в художественных текстах, которые неизбежны при переводе информации с английского языка на узбекский, предоставляя лингвистам огромный объем эмпирических данных для изучения. Переводчики неизбежно вынуждены прибегать к различным "трансформациям" для достижения прагматической адаптации текста. Опытный переводчик должен перевести оригинальный текст ясно и точно, сохранив при этом максимальный уровень адекватности. Преодоление субъективизма и случайных ошибок автора - необходимость при использовании перевода в качестве источника для лингвистического исследования.*

Ключевые слова: *исходный текст, трансформации, методы, лексические трансформации, замены, добавления, опущения, эквивалентность, семантические компоненты.*

Translation transformations are technical techniques and methods of translation, which consist of transforming the text by replacing units of the source language with communicatively equivalent units of the target language if it is impossible to use regular correspondences in a given context. In addition, translation transformations are called language expressions that are obtained as a result of the use of such techniques and methods. According to many linguists, transformations, which consist of changing the formal or semantic components of the source text, are the basis of most modern translation techniques. Translation transformations are aimed at achieving the main goal of translation - the creation of an adequate and equivalent translation. This means that the semantic content of the source text and its functional and stylistic characteristics must be fully conveyed.

The main feature of translation transformations is that the translation uses a unit of the target language that is not typical for a given unit of the source language (that is, irregular,

contextual correspondences). This is done to provide the most accurate translation (compared to using regular matches in a particular context).

The implementation of translation transformations is possible due to several translation techniques: in particular, the methods of displacement, lexical additions, and omissions. The movement technique involves the use of an irregular correspondence in a different (than in the original) place of the utterance. Omission means the translator's rejection of the words of the original, which are semantically redundant, irrelevant, and easily recoverable in context. Lexical additions convey the semantic components of the original that were left unexpressed.

As a rule, we can talk about the following tasks that can be solved by applying translation transformations:

- Bring the translation closer to the norms of the target language;
- Prevent the use of word-building models that are alien to the target language;
- Minimize the use of literalisms in translation (that is, errors associated with literal translation);
- Improving the naturalness, aesthetics, compactness, clarity, and consistency of the translation text;
- Save readers from redundant information and focus their attention on important background information;
- To convey in translation the stylistic figures of the text, which were created by a difficult-to-transfer wordplay.

So, according to one of the concepts, translation transformations can be considered as a set of four main types of changes. These include the following changes:

- Permutations are changes (compared to the original text) in the order and location in the translation text of language elements (as a rule, words and phrases);
- Substitutions are changes in the grammatical (members of a sentence, parts of speech, types of syntactic connection) and lexical (concretization, compensation, anatomical translation) components of the original text;
- Additions - this is the use of additional language units in the translation text, the correspondence of which is not in the original text;
- Omission is the opposite of adding language units.

Depending on the nature of deviations from interlingual correspondences, translation transformations can be classified in the following way:

- Lexical translation transformations;
- Grammatical translation transformations;
- Complex lexico-grammatical (mixed) translation transformations.

Lexical translation transformations have found their application when it is necessary to translate a non-standard language unit (usually a word). Similar units are used in the source language to denote objects that are found only in the source culture (or traditional names characteristic only of it), terms in professional fields, as well as proper names.

Non-standard language units are relatively independent of context. But despite this, they are still able to give the translated text a certain direction, which determines their important role in the translation process.

Lexical transformation can be carried out using such techniques as transcription (transcription) and transliteration, tracing, lexico-semantic substitutions (including generalization, concretization, modulation or semantic development, holistic transformation), and contextual replacement (that is, occasional correspondence). The essence of grammatical transformations is to transform the sentence structure in the process of translation and bring it into line with the norms of the target language. The need for this transformation is due to differences in the grammatical structure between the source and target languages. The number of grammatical transformations includes syntactic assimilation, division or union of a sentence, and purely grammatical substitutions. Complex transformation techniques transform both the vocabulary and the syntactic structure of the original text. Among them, antonymic translation, explication (or descriptive translation), and compensation are distinguished.

It is necessary to look at the examples through comparison of the piece from the story “The Pacing Mustang” written by Ernest Seton Thompson and its translation into Uzbek done by Toghay Murad.

- En: "Seventeen minutes," said the cook, glancing at the Waterbury, with the air of a train-starter, though this show of precision had never yet been justified by events.
- Uz: “Yana o’n yeti minutdan keyin, - javob berdi oshpaz, stansiya boshliqlari kabi soatiga jiddiy qarab. Oshpaz og’izda juda tayin gapirar, amalda esa betayin edi.”
- Literal translation: “O'n yetti daqiqa, - dedi oshpaz Uoterberiga ko'z tashlab, poezdni ishga tushiruvchilar kabi. Garchi bunday aniqlik hech qachon voqealar bilan oqlanmagan.”

The literal translation is inaccurate, therefore, should be avoided. In the adequate translation there are a variety of transformations applied. First of all, addition is used in the expression “Yana o’n yetti minutdan keyin”, which means “After seventeen minutes”. Second, the word “said” is originally translated like “dedi”, however the translator tried to clarify that it was an answer to the question and altered it to “javob berdi”. Third, Waterbury is the brand of the watch, popular in Europe or the US, but for non-English speakers it could be unclear in the context. That is why the translator opted for generalization referring to “soat”. Next, according to the Free Dictionary “the air of something is a manner, affectation, appearance, or behavior indicative of some quality or trait” and it shows that “with the the air of train-starter” implies to the behavior of the man working in the train station. It is difficult to know what kind of people they are and in the translation it is concretized through the word “jiddiy qarab”, which is “looking serious” and “poezd boshqaruvchisi (train-starter) was substituted by “stansiya rahbari” (the head of the station).

One sentence is divided into two to ensure that the text is understood well by the audience. The last sentence in the target text is more specific or concrete and says that he is often good at talking, than doing his job.

- En: “...though this show of precision had never yet been justified by events.”
- Uz: “Oshpaz og’izda juda tayin gapirar, amalda esa betayin edi.”
- Literal translation: “Garchi bunday aniqlik hech qachon voqealar bilan oqlanmagan.”

If a translator does not try to get the hidden meaning behind the text, the reader will get confused. Thus, transformations as special methods of logical thinking contribute to the preservation of information that is subject to translation. Modern linguistics has not yet developed a unified and universal classification of translation transformations. Some of them are too broad,

others too narrow. Translators usually take one of these classifications as a basis, and then creatively rethink and supplement it.

REFERENCES

1. Shvaytser A.D. Translation and linguistics .M. 1973.
2. Levitskaya T.R, Fiterman A.M. The problem of Translation on the material of the contemporary English language. M. 1974
3. Salomov G. Tarjima nazariyasiga kirish. T. 1978.
4. Klaudy, K. (1996). Concretization and generalization of meaning in translation.
5. Barkhudarov .1975. L.S. Language and Translation. (Issues on General and Concrete Theory of Translation). –M.: International Relations, 240 p
6. General Linguistic Problems of Translation// Nauka and Sovremennost. № 13-3. – P. 18-21.
7. Komissarov V. N. 2002. Contemporary Translation Studies. – M.: «ETS» Publishing House, 406 p.
8. Tirkkonen-Condit, S. and R. Jääskeläinen (eds) (2000) Tapping and Mapping the Processes of Translation and Interpreting, Amsterdam and Philadelphia: John Benjamins.
9. Spivak, G. (1993/2000) ‘The Politics of Translation’, in G. Spivak Outside in the Teaching Machine, London and New York: Routledge, reprinted in L. Venuti (ed.) (2000), pp. 397–416.
10. Newmark, P. (1981) Approaches to Translation. Oxford: Pergamon.
11. (Wild Animals I Have Known : And 200 Drawings : Seton, Ernest Thompson, 1860-1946 : Free Download, Borrow, and Streaming : Internet Archive, 2007b)
12. (Сетон-Томпсон, Эрнест - Мустанг-иноходец : Рассказы О Животных : [Для Детей] - Search RSL, n.d.-b)